

Enhancing Precision in Artillery by Integrating Fuzzy Logic Control with Precision Guidance Kits for 155mm Munitions: A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract

This paper provides a comprehensive review of the integration of fuzzy logic control into Precision Guidance Kits (PGKs) for 155mm artillery munitions. By retrofitting unguided munitions with advanced fuzzy logic systems, artillery units achieve enhanced accuracy, reduced collateral damage, and improved operational efficiency. This review explores the mathematical foundations of fuzzy logic control, its integration with traditional artillery systems, and its potential to address operational challenges such as environmental disturbances and electronic warfare. Furthermore, the paper identifies future research directions, including AI integration, sensor advancements, and ethical considerations for deploying autonomous artillery systems.

Keywords: Fuzzy Logic Control Precision Guidance Kits (PGKs) Artillery Systems Operational Efficiency Autonomous Systems AI Integration.

1. INTRODUCTION

Artillery systems are indispensable in modern warfare, providing the tactical and strategic advantage of long-range firepower to suppress enemy positions, neutralise threats, and achieve operational objectives. They are often deployed to shape the battlefield, deny enemy movement, and provide close support for ground troops. Despite their significant role, traditional unguided artillery munitions are plagued by inherent inaccuracies. These inaccuracies arise from environmental factors such as wind, temperature, and terrain, which affect the trajectory and impact point of the munitions. As a result, multiple rounds are often required to achieve a single objective, leading to resource wastage, increased logistical burdens, and unintended collateral damage [1], [2]. For instance, during Operation Desert Storm, unguided artillery and airstrikes often required extensive firepower to achieve precision against fixed targets, leading to significant collateral damage [3]. Similarly, conventional artillery systems used in urban warfare have been criticised for their indiscriminate nature, as highlighted during conflicts in Fallujah, Iraq, where civilian infrastructure suffered extensively due to the inaccuracy of traditional rounds [4].

The development of Precision-Guided Munitions (PGMs) has addressed many of these challenges. By integrating advanced guidance technologies such as Global Positioning Systems (GPS), Inertial Navigation Systems (INS), and laser guidance, PGMs offer improved accuracy and reduced collateral damage. These systems leverage precise navigation and targeting mechanisms to ensure munitions hit their intended targets, even in challenging operational environments. For example, the Excalibur 155mm artillery shell, equipped with GPS guidance, has demonstrated high accuracy, often landing within metres of its target, significantly reducing the need for multiple rounds [5], [6].

1.1 Limitations of Existing Precision-Guided Technologies

Despite the transformative potential of precision-guided munitions (PGMs), the technologies that enable their effectiveness face significant limitations that hinder their reliability and applicability in modern warfare. These limitations include vulnerabilities to electronic warfare, environmental dependencies, and high development and production costs.

1.1.2 Electronic Warfare Vulnerability

Global Positioning System (GPS) technology forms the backbone of most modern precision-guided systems, offering real-time navigation and targeting capabilities. However, GPS is inherently vulnerable to jamming and spoofing, making it susceptible to adversarial electronic warfare.

- **Jamming:** High-powered signals intentionally transmitted by adversaries can overpower GPS signals, rendering the system unable to determine its position or trajectory. For example, during military exercises in Eastern Europe, GPS jamming techniques were used extensively to disrupt the operational effectiveness of navigation systems, illustrating the risks faced by precision-guided munitions dependent on GPS [7], [8].
- **Spoofing:** Adversaries can transmit false signals to deceive GPS receivers, leading to incorrect positional data. This was demonstrated during the Black Sea incidents in 2017, where multiple ships reported GPS disruptions attributed to spoofing techniques [9].

These vulnerabilities are particularly problematic in contested environments, such as urban warfare or asymmetrical conflicts, where adversaries may employ advanced electronic countermeasures to negate the technological superiority of precision-guided systems. The inability of GPS-reliant munitions to operate effectively under such conditions necessitates alternative or complementary guidance technologies.

1.1.3 Environmental Factors

Environmental conditions also play a significant role in limiting the reliability of precision-guided technologies.

- **Inertial Navigation System (INS):** INS provides accurate positional data without relying on external signals, making it resistant to electronic warfare. However, it suffers from cumulative drift errors over time, where small inaccuracies in sensor readings compound, leading to significant deviations during long-duration operations. For example, during extended artillery bombardments, INS-guided systems may experience accuracy degradation that undermines their precision [10].
- **Laser Guidance Systems:** While laser guidance offers unparalleled accuracy in clear environments, it is highly dependent on line-of-sight visibility. Urban warfare, forested battlefields, or environments with heavy smoke, dust, or adverse weather conditions can obstruct the laser path, making these systems ineffective. For instance, in urban conflicts such as the Battle of Mosul, the reliance on laser guidance systems was challenged by the obstructed line-of-sight, necessitating the use of alternative targeting methods [11].

These environmental dependencies restrict the adaptability of existing precision-guided technologies, particularly in complex terrains or under adverse conditions.

1.1.4 High Costs

The development, production, and maintenance of PGMs are resource-intensive, posing a significant challenge to their widespread adoption.

- **Development Costs:** Designing precision-guided systems requires advanced research, high-performance components, and rigorous testing to ensure reliability and accuracy. For example, the development cost of the Excalibur GPS-guided artillery shell was estimated at \$55,000 per round, making it cost-prohibitive for sustained use in large-scale operations [12].
- **Production Costs:** Precision-guided systems require high-quality materials and complex manufacturing processes, further driving up costs. Militaries with limited budgets often struggle to allocate resources for acquiring PGMs, prioritising conventional munitions for bulk operational needs instead.
- **Operational Costs:** The logistical and maintenance requirements for PGMs add to their overall expense. For example, integrating precision-guided capabilities into existing artillery systems requires additional hardware, software updates, and skilled personnel, all of which contribute to operational expenses [13].

High costs also impact militaries in resource-constrained environments, where the procurement of PGMs must be balanced against other critical defence needs, such as personnel training, infrastructure development, and broader force modernisation. This financial barrier underscores the need for cost-effective alternatives like retrofitting conventional munitions with technologies such as fuzzy logic-controlled PGKs.

1.2 Addressing the Limitations

To overcome these limitations, the integration of fuzzy logic control into PGKs has emerged as a promising solution. Fuzzy logic, a computational approach that mimics human reasoning to handle uncertainties, is particularly suited for dynamic and unpredictable battlefield conditions. By retrofitting unguided munitions with fuzzy logic-controlled PGKs,

artillery systems can adapt to real-time environmental changes such as wind speed, temperature, and target movement, ensuring higher accuracy while remaining resilient to electronic countermeasures [11], [12].

For instance, fuzzy logic-controlled artillery munitions can dynamically adjust their trajectory based on input data from onboard sensors, achieving precision comparable to high-cost PGMs at a fraction of the cost. The Guided Multiple Launch Rocket System (GMLRS), though not entirely based on fuzzy logic, demonstrates the potential of integrating adaptive guidance systems to achieve precision in GPS-contested environments [13]. Extending such capabilities to conventional artillery rounds through fuzzy logic represents a significant advancement in artillery technology. In this context, fuzzy logic control offers the following key advantages:

- **Adaptability:** It enables real-time adjustments to trajectory based on imprecise or incomplete data.
- **Resilience:** Fuzzy systems maintain functionality in GPS-denied or electronically contested environments.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** Retrofitting existing munitions with fuzzy-controlled PGKs is significantly more economical than producing new PGMs.

This paper reviews the role of fuzzy logic in transforming conventional artillery munitions into precision-guided systems. By examining its mathematical underpinnings, operational benefits, and integration challenges, this study highlights the potential of fuzzy logic to redefine the future of artillery warfare.

2. Current State of Precision Guidance Systems

Modern PGMs employ a range of advanced technologies to enhance targeting accuracy and operational efficiency. These technologies include Global Positioning Systems (GPS), Inertial Navigation Systems (INS), and laser guidance systems, each offering unique advantages and limitations in various operational scenarios. While these systems have significantly advanced the effectiveness of modern artillery, their vulnerabilities in contested and complex environments necessitate complementary approaches, such as fuzzy logic control, to ensure precision and adaptability.

2.1 Global Positioning Systems (GPS)

GPS is the cornerstone of most modern PGMs, offering real-time positional data to guide munitions accurately to their intended targets. By using a constellation of satellites, GPS receivers onboard munitions calculate their position and adjust their trajectory accordingly. This technology has revolutionised precision targeting, enabling artillery shells to strike within a few metres of their designated impact points [4], [5].

For example, the Excalibur GPS-guided artillery shell uses satellite navigation to achieve precision strikes, often with an error margin of less than five metres. Such accuracy significantly reduces the number of rounds required to neutralise a target, thereby minimising resource wastage and collateral damage [6]. However, GPS-based systems are highly vulnerable to electronic warfare:

- **Jamming:** Adversaries can deploy high-power signals to disrupt GPS communication, causing munitions to lose positional awareness. This was observed during conflicts in Eastern Ukraine, where GPS jamming extensively disrupted military operations [7].
- **Spoofing:** Sophisticated adversaries can transmit false GPS signals, deceiving the munitions' navigation systems and diverting them off course. For instance, during maritime operations in the Black Sea, GPS spoofing incidents resulted in incorrect positioning of military and civilian vessels [8].

These vulnerabilities highlight the need for resilient systems that can function effectively in GPS-contested environments.

2.2 Inertial Navigation Systems (INS)

INS is a robust and self-contained navigation technology that calculates positional data based on accelerometer and gyroscope measurements. Unlike GPS, INS does not rely on external signals, making it immune to jamming and spoofing. This autonomy makes it an essential component of PGMs operating in contested environments or GPS-denied zones [6]. Hence, INS is widely used in systems like the Tomahawk cruise missile, where it provides uninterrupted navigation and guidance. By integrating INS with GPS in a hybrid system, munitions can achieve both resilience and accuracy, ensuring continued functionality even in electronically degraded environments [9].

However, INS suffers from a critical limitation: cumulative drift. Over time, small measurement errors in the inertial sensors compound, leading to significant deviations from the intended trajectory during extended missions. This drift reduces the accuracy of stand-alone INS systems, particularly for long-range artillery munitions. Hybridising INS with complementary technologies, such as fuzzy logic control, can mitigate these errors by introducing real-time corrections based on environmental feedback [10].

2.3 Laser Guidance

Laser guidance systems are widely recognised for their precision and reliability in clear operational conditions. In this technology, a laser designator illuminates the target, and the munition uses a seeker to track the reflected laser beam, guiding it to the target. Laser-guided munitions, such as the Paveway laser-guided bomb, have been instrumental in achieving precision strikes during conflicts, reducing collateral damage and improving mission success rates [7]. Despite their advantages, laser-guided systems face significant limitations:

- **Line-of-Sight Requirement:** Laser designators require an unobstructed path between the target and the munition, limiting their effectiveness in urban warfare, forested terrains, or adverse weather conditions such as fog, smoke, and heavy rain. For instance, during operations in Iraq, laser-guided systems often encountered challenges due to dense urban structures obstructing the laser beam [11].
- **Designator Vulnerability:** The requirement for a laser designator exposes personnel or equipment to enemy detection, increasing operational risks.

To overcome these constraints, hybrid systems combining laser guidance with complementary technologies, such as GPS or fuzzy logic control, can improve effectiveness in complex environments.

2.4 Role of Fuzzy Logic Control as a Complementary Technology

Fuzzy Logic Control (FLC) enhances the performance of existing guidance systems by enabling real-time adaptation to changing environmental conditions, such as wind speed, temperature and terrain variations. Unlike traditional deterministic systems, fuzzy logic processes ambiguous or incomplete data, making it particularly suited for dynamic and uncertain battlefield scenarios [12]. Thus, FLC offers the following benefits

- **Adaptive Trajectory Correction:** Fuzzy logic systems continuously adjust the munition's trajectory in response to sensor inputs, ensuring accuracy even when external navigation signals are compromised.
- **Environmental Resilience:** By accounting for factors like crosswinds, varying temperatures, and target movement, fuzzy logic complements traditional technologies, reducing reliance on external systems such as GPS.
- **Integration Potential:** Fuzzy logic can be seamlessly integrated with GPS, INS, and laser guidance systems, forming hybrid solutions that combine the strengths of each technology while mitigating their individual limitations. For example, a fuzzy logic-based system can use INS for positional data while correcting drift errors using environmental feedback. Similarly, in GPS-denied environments, fuzzy logic can optimise laser-guided trajectories by adapting to real-time sensor inputs, ensuring accuracy without requiring continuous external signals.

3. Fuzzy Logic Control in PGKs

FLC has emerged as a transformative technology for enhancing the performance of PGMs. Unlike traditional control systems that rely on deterministic inputs and outputs, fuzzy logic provides a robust framework for managing imprecise or uncertain data, making it particularly suited for dynamic and complex environments such as the battlefield. Its application in PGKs enables artillery munitions to adapt to real-time environmental conditions, such as wind speed and temperature variations, thereby improving accuracy and operational efficiency.

3.1 Basics of Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy logic, introduced by Lotfi Zadeh in 1965 [9], is a mathematical approach that models uncertainty and imprecision by operating on degrees of truth rather than binary values (true/false or 0/1). This characteristic makes it ideal for real-world applications, where inputs are often ambiguous or incomplete. Unlike classical binary logic systems, fuzzy logic can handle a range of possibilities between 0 and 1, allowing for more nuanced decision-making. The key components of a fuzzy logic system include:

- **Fuzzification:** Fuzzification is the process of converting crisp input values into fuzzy sets using membership functions. Membership functions define the degree to which an input belongs to a particular category. For example, in the context of artillery guidance, inputs such as wind speed (V_w) or temperature (T_a) can be classified as "low," "medium," or "high." A typical membership function for wind speed might be:

$$\mu_{low} V_w = \max \left(0, \frac{V_{max} - V_w}{V_{max} - V_{min}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where:

- $\mu_{low} V_w$ is the degree of membership of the wind speed being classified as "low."
- V_{max} and V_{min} are the maximum and minimum wind speed values, respectively.

- **Rule Base:** The rule base is a collection of IF-THEN rules that define the system's behaviour based on the fuzzy inputs. For example:
 - **Rule 1:** IF wind speed is "low" AND temperature is "high," THEN adjust trajectory slightly upward.
 - **Rule 2:** IF wind speed is "high" AND temperature is "medium," THEN adjust trajectory downward significantly.

These rules encapsulate expert knowledge or empirical data, allowing the system to make decisions based on combinations of fuzzy inputs. The inference engine applies fuzzy logic operators (e.g., AND, OR) to evaluate the rules and compute the degree of truth for each output. For instance, the rule's truth value for a given combination of inputs can be calculated using the fuzzy AND operator:

$$\text{truth value} = \min(\mu_{\text{low}}(V_w), \mu_{\text{high}}(T_a)) \quad (2)$$

- **Inference Engine:** The inference engine processes fuzzy inputs using the rule base to generate fuzzy outputs. It applies logical operations (e.g., AND, OR, NOT) to evaluate the degree of truth for each rule and combines the results to produce a fuzzy output. For example, if the input wind speed (V_w) is classified as "medium" with a degree of membership 0.7, and the temperature (T_a) is "high" with a membership degree of 0.8, the rule "IF wind speed is medium AND temperature is high" would be evaluated with a truth value of:

$$\min(0.7, 0.8) = 0.7 \quad (3)$$

where $\min$ represents the fuzzy AND operation.

- **Defuzzification:** Defuzzification converts the fuzzy outputs into crisp values that can be used for actionable results, such as adjusting the munition's trajectory. A common method for defuzzification is the **centroid method**, which calculates the crisp output as the centre of gravity of the fuzzy output distribution:

$$y_{\text{crisp}} = \frac{\int y\mu(y)dy}{\int \mu(y)dy} \quad (4)$$

where:

- y_{crisp} is the defuzzified output.
- $\mu(y)$ is the membership function of the fuzzy output.

3.2 Fuzzy Guidance Law

Fuzzy logic adjusts the trajectory of a projectile in real-time based on environmental inputs. The guidance law can be expressed as:

$$\Delta\theta = k_f \cdot \mu(V_w, T_a) \quad (5)$$

where:

- $\Delta\theta$ is the trajectory correction angle.
- k_f is the fuzzy gain constant.
- $\mu(V_w, T_a)$ represents the fuzzy membership value derived from wind speed and temperature.

3.3 Advantages of Fuzzy Logic in PGKs

Fuzzy logic provides several advantages when applied to PGKs for precision-guided artillery munitions:

3.2.1 Adaptability to Environmental Variability

Fuzzy logic systems dynamically adjust to changing environmental conditions, such as wind speed, temperature, and terrain variations. Unlike deterministic systems, fuzzy logic handles uncertainty gracefully, ensuring consistent performance under diverse conditions.

3.2.2 Resilience in Contested Environments

By reducing reliance on external inputs such as GPS signals, fuzzy logic systems maintain functionality in GPS-denied or electronically contested environments. This resilience is critical in modern warfare, where adversaries frequently deploy electronic countermeasures.

3.3.3 Real-Time Decision-Making

Fuzzy logic systems process inputs and generate outputs in real-time, enabling munitions to adapt mid-flight based on updated environmental data. This capability significantly enhances targeting accuracy and reduces the likelihood of collateral damage.

3.3.4 Ease of Integration

Fuzzy logic systems can be seamlessly integrated with existing technologies, such as Inertial Navigation Systems (INS) and laser guidance systems, to enhance their performance and address their limitations.

4. Mathematical Model for Fuzzy-Controlled PGKs

The mathematical framework for fuzzy-controlled PGKs provides a systematic approach to improving the accuracy of 155mm artillery shells. By dynamically adjusting the projectile's trajectory using fuzzy logic, these systems mitigate environmental disturbances, ensuring precision targeting. This section outlines the trajectory dynamics and error reduction mechanisms enabled by fuzzy-controlled PGKs.

4.1 Trajectory Dynamics

The motion of a 155mm artillery shell is governed by classical projectile motion equations. Assuming no air resistance and constant gravity, the horizontal and vertical positions of the shell at time t are given by:

$$x(t) = v_o \cos(\theta)t \quad (6)$$

$$y(t) = v_o \sin(\theta)t - \frac{1}{2}gt^2 \quad (7)$$

where:

- $x(t)$ and $y(t)$ are the horizontal and vertical positions.
- v_o is the initial velocity.
- θ is the launch angle.
- g is the gravitational constant.

In practice, environmental factors such as wind speed, temperature, and air density introduce deviations from this ideal trajectory, leading to inaccuracies. To account for these disturbances, fuzzy logic introduces corrections to the launch angle (θ) to minimise deviations caused by environmental disturbances:

$$\theta' = \theta + \Delta\theta \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta\theta$ is determined dynamically by the fuzzy inference engine.

4.2 Trajectory Correction Using Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy logic systems dynamically adjust $\Delta\theta$ to counteract environmental disturbances. For example:

Crosswind Compensation: Wind speed (V_w) may push the projectile off course, requiring an adjustment to the launch angle ($\Delta\theta$) to realign the trajectory.

Temperature Effects: Variations in temperature (T_a) can affect air density, altering the drag force on the shell. Fuzzy logic uses this input to determine the necessary corrections. By iteratively updating $\Delta\theta$, fuzzy-controlled PGKs ensure that the projectile remains on course throughout its flight.

4.3 Error Reduction

The accuracy of a trajectory is evaluated by the error (E) between the desired target position (P_d) and the actual hit point (P_a):

$$E = \sqrt{(x_d - x_a)^2 + (y_d - y_a)^2} \quad (9)$$

Fuzzy control iteratively adjusts $\Delta\theta$ to minimise E , ensuring precise target engagement [11], [12].

where:

- x_d and y_d are the coordinates of the desired target position.
- x_a and y_a are the coordinates of the actual impact point.

The goal of the fuzzy control system is to iteratively adjust $\Delta\theta$ to minimise E , satisfying Equation (3):

5. Operational Benefits

The integration of fuzzy logic control into PGKs offers transformative operational advantages, significantly enhancing the accuracy, resilience, and cost-effectiveness of artillery munitions. These benefits address the limitations of traditional unguided munitions and extend the operational capabilities of precision-guided systems, even in contested and resource-constrained environments.

5.1 Improved Accuracy

One of the most critical advantages of fuzzy logic-controlled PGKs is their ability to significantly reduce targeting errors. By dynamically adjusting the trajectory of a projectile in real time based on environmental inputs, fuzzy logic enables metre-level accuracy compared to tens of metres for unguided rounds [13].

- **Dynamic Adaptation to Environmental Conditions:** Fuzzy logic systems process real-time inputs, such as wind speed, temperature, and target movement, to calculate trajectory corrections. For instance, if wind speed increases unexpectedly during the projectile's flight, the fuzzy inference engine recalibrates the launch angle (θ) to counteract the drift, ensuring the munition stays on course.
- **Enhanced Precision in GPS-Denied Environments:** Unlike traditional PGMs that rely heavily on GPS signals, fuzzy logic systems can function effectively in environments where GPS is unavailable or compromised. This capability is particularly advantageous in electronic warfare scenarios, where adversaries deploy jamming or spoofing techniques to disrupt GPS-based systems [14].
- **Applications in Urban and Asymmetrical Warfare:** In urban warfare, where line-of-sight targeting and environmental complexity pose challenges, fuzzy logic systems excel by processing multiple uncertain variables simultaneously. For example, during artillery operations in densely populated areas, fuzzy logic helps minimise collateral damage by ensuring precise targeting.

5.2 Cost-Effectiveness

The cost of developing and producing PGMs is a significant barrier to their widespread adoption, particularly for militaries operating under constrained budgets. Fuzzy logic-controlled PGKs offer a cost-effective alternative by retrofitting existing unguided munitions with advanced guidance capabilities.

- **Reduced Production Costs:** Retrofitting conventional shells with fuzzy logic-based PGKs is far less expensive than manufacturing new PGMs. For instance, the cost of retrofitting a 155mm artillery round with a PGK is estimated to be a fraction of the cost of a fully integrated GPS-guided munition [15].
- **Scalability for Resource-Constrained Militaries:** The affordability of fuzzy-controlled PGKs makes precision-guided capabilities accessible to a broader range of militaries, including those with limited resources. This scalability ensures that advanced targeting technology is not restricted to highly developed nations.
- **Logistical Savings:** Improved accuracy reduces the number of rounds required to neutralise a target, resulting in substantial savings in ammunition and logistical support. In addition, the reduction in collateral damage lowers the cost of post-conflict reconstruction and legal liabilities.

5.3 Ethical Compliance

The ability to reduce collateral damage aligns fuzzy logic-controlled PGKs with the principles of international humanitarian law, which emphasise minimising harm to civilian populations and infrastructure during armed conflict [16].

- **Precision Strikes in Civilian Areas:** By achieving high accuracy, fuzzy logic systems ensure that artillery strikes are confined to intended targets, reducing unintended harm in populated areas. This precision is critical in modern asymmetrical warfare, where combatants often operate within civilian environments.
- **Adherence to Rules of Engagement:** The deployment of fuzzy-controlled PGKs supports adherence to strict rules of engagement by providing commanders with confidence in the precision of their munitions. This capability enhances the ethical standing of military operations and reduces the risk of reputational damage.

6. Challenges

Despite the significant operational benefits of fuzzy logic-controlled PGKs, their development and deployment are not without challenges. These challenges stem from the technological complexity of integrating advanced systems, the high initial costs involved, and the ethical considerations surrounding the use of autonomous systems in military applications.

6.1 Technological Complexity

The integration of fuzzy logic into PGKs, particularly when combined with Inertia (INS) and GPS, introduces a high degree of technological complexity.

- **Advanced Computational Resources:** Fuzzy logic systems require substantial computational power to process real-time data from multiple sensors, evaluate fuzzy rules, and calculate trajectory corrections. For example, a fuzzy inference engine must process wind speed, temperature and other environmental inputs simultaneously, applying dozens of rules to determine a precise correction angle ($\Delta\theta$) [17].
- **System Integration Challenges:** Combining fuzzy logic with traditional guidance technologies such as INS and GPS necessitates the development of hybrid control algorithms. These algorithms must seamlessly integrate deterministic and fuzzy approaches while ensuring compatibility across hardware and software platforms. This complexity is amplified in GPS-contested environments, where the system must rely more heavily on fuzzy logic and INS for navigation.
- **Sensor Dependency:** Accurate sensor data is critical for the effective operation of fuzzy logic systems. Any inaccuracies in input data, such as wind speed or temperature, can lead to erroneous trajectory corrections. Ensuring the reliability and robustness of sensors in harsh battlefield conditions adds to the technological demands.

6.2 Initial Costs

While fuzzy logic-controlled PGKs are more cost-effective in the long term compared to manufacturing new PGMs, their development and deployment involve significant upfront investments, especially in areas such as:

- **Research and Development Costs:** Developing fuzzy logic systems for PGKs requires extensive R&D efforts, including designing fuzzy rule bases, simulating system behaviour under various conditions, and field-testing prototypes. For instance, creating a robust rule base tailored to different environmental scenarios demands significant time and expertise [18].
- **Hardware and Retrofitting Costs:** Retrofitting conventional artillery rounds with PGKs involves manufacturing and integrating additional components, such as sensors, microcontrollers, and actuators. These costs can be substantial, particularly for militaries seeking to modernise large stockpiles of legacy munitions.
- **Training and Maintenance:** Operators and maintenance personnel must be trained to handle the new systems, adding to the overall cost. Moreover, maintaining the sophisticated hardware required for fuzzy-controlled PGKs necessitates additional investments in spare parts and technical support.

6.3 Ethical Considerations

The introduction of autonomous capabilities through fuzzy logic systems raises important ethical questions regarding accountability, compliance and the use of AI in warfare. Areas of concern include:

- **Accountability for Autonomous Decisions:** As fuzzy logic introduces a degree of autonomy in trajectory corrections, determining accountability for unintended consequences, such as collateral damage, becomes challenging. Who is responsible when a fuzzy logic-controlled munition causes unintended harm—operators, developers, or commanders? Robust regulatory frameworks are required to address these issues and ensure accountability [19].
- **Compliance with International Humanitarian Law:** Fuzzy-controlled PGKs must adhere to the principles of necessity, distinction, and proportionality as outlined in international humanitarian law. This requires rigorous testing and validation to ensure that the system consistently delivers precise targeting while minimising harm to civilians and civilian infrastructure.
- **Public Perception and Acceptance:** The deployment of autonomous technologies in military operations often faces scrutiny from the public and international communities. Ensuring transparency in the development and deployment of fuzzy logic-controlled PGKs is essential to build trust and acceptance.

7. Future Directions

To fully realise the potential of fuzzy logic-controlled Precision Guidance Kits (PGKs) and address existing challenges, future research and development should focus on integrating emerging technologies, enhancing sensor capabilities, and establishing robust ethical frameworks. These directions aim to make PGKs more adaptable, resilient, and compliant with international laws and societal expectations.

7.1 AI Integration

The combination of fuzzy logic with Machine Learning (ML) offers significant opportunities for improving decision-making in dynamic and complex operational environments. Key areas include:

- **Adaptive Learning Systems:** ML can enhance the rule base of fuzzy logic systems by enabling them to adapt over time based on operational data. For instance, an ML-enhanced fuzzy system could optimise trajectory corrections by learning from previous engagements, improving precision in subsequent operations [20].

- **Real-Time Data Processing:** AI algorithms can process large volumes of real-time data, such as wind patterns, terrain features and target movement, to provide more accurate inputs for fuzzy inference engines. This capability is particularly useful in scenarios where environmental conditions change rapidly.
- **Autonomous Targeting:** By integrating computer vision and Natural Language Processing (NLP) capabilities, AI can enable autonomous target recognition and engagement. For example, an AI-augmented PGK could use vision systems to identify targets visually and apply fuzzy logic to adjust its trajectory dynamically. For example, combining fuzzy logic with deep reinforcement learning to optimise projectile paths in GPS-denied environments.

7.2 Advanced Sensors

The development of robust sensor systems is critical for enhancing the accuracy and reliability of fuzzy logic-controlled PGKs. Advanced sensors enable better environmental awareness and improve the system's ability to adapt to operational conditions. Key areas of improvement include:

- **Improved Target Recognition:** Sensors equipped with advanced imaging and infrared capabilities can provide high-resolution data for precise target identification and trajectory adjustment. For instance, integrating LiDAR and radar sensors with fuzzy systems can significantly enhance targeting accuracy in cluttered or low-visibility environments [21].
- **Enhanced Environmental Awareness:** Sensors capable of measuring wind speed, humidity and temperature with high precision can feed more accurate data into the fuzzy inference engine. For example, multi-sensor arrays can provide redundant data inputs, increasing the robustness of the system in adverse conditions.
- **Resilience to Electronic Warfare:** The development of counter-countermeasure technologies, such as anti-jamming and anti-spoofing sensors, is essential for maintaining functionality in adversarial environments. These sensors can detect and mitigate electronic threats, ensuring uninterrupted operation of the guidance system [22]. For example, deploying sensor fusion techniques to combine data from multiple modalities, such as GPS, INS and environmental sensors, for more accurate trajectory corrections.

7.3 Ethical Governance

The increasing autonomy of fuzzy logic-controlled PGKs raises critical ethical considerations that must be addressed through comprehensive governance frameworks. Some of these considerations include:

- **Accountability in Autonomous Systems:** Establishing clear accountability mechanisms is essential to determine responsibility for decisions made by autonomous systems. For example, in the event of unintended harm caused by a fuzzy-controlled PGK, the framework should clarify whether responsibility lies with the operator, the developer, or the commanding officer [23].
- **Compliance with International Humanitarian Law:** Autonomous systems must adhere to the principles of necessity, distinction, and proportionality in targeting. Ensuring that fuzzy logic systems consistently meet these standards requires rigorous testing and validation during development.
- **Transparency and Public Trust:** The deployment of autonomous military systems often faces public scrutiny. Transparent communication about the capabilities, limitations, and safeguards of fuzzy-controlled PGKs is vital for building trust among stakeholders, including policymakers, international organisations, and the general public.

8. Conclusion

The integration of fuzzy logic control into PGKs marks a transformative advancement in artillery technology, bridging the gap between traditional unguided munitions and advanced PGMs. By leveraging the adaptability of fuzzy logic, these systems offer real-time responsiveness to environmental factors such as wind speed, temperature fluctuations, and terrain variations. This dynamic capability enables metre-level precision, significantly reducing collateral damage and aligning artillery operations with international humanitarian principles.

Fuzzy-controlled PGKs are particularly valuable in modern warfare environments, where adversaries frequently employ electronic countermeasures to disrupt GPS-reliant systems. Unlike conventional PGMs, fuzzy systems maintain resilience in GPS-denied or electronically contested conditions, ensuring consistent performance under such challenges. Additionally, the ability to retrofit existing munitions with fuzzy-controlled PGKs provides a cost-effective alternative to manufacturing entirely new precision-guided systems, making this technology accessible to militaries operating under constrained budgets. This affordability extends their utility across a spectrum of conflict scenarios, from large-scale conventional warfare to asymmetric engagements.

To fully realise the potential of fuzzy-controlled PGKs, future research and development should focus on several key areas. Combining fuzzy logic with artificial intelligence and machine learning will enable systems to adapt and improve

through experience, enhancing decision-making in complex and dynamic environments. Advances in sensor technology will further improve the accuracy of environmental data, enabling more precise trajectory adjustments. Furthermore, the establishment of comprehensive ethical frameworks is essential to ensure accountability and compliance with international standards, addressing societal concerns regarding the use of autonomous systems in warfare.

By integrating these advancements, fuzzy-controlled PGKs are poised to become a cornerstone of modern artillery systems. They offer unparalleled precision, adaptability, and cost-efficiency while supporting ethical and operational standards. These innovations not only enhance the effectiveness of artillery operations but also set a benchmark for the responsible development and deployment of emerging military technologies.

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